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CHARACTERISTICS OF CALCIUM HOMEOSTASIS IN PATIENTS WITH KIDNEY DAMAGE WITH CALCIUM DEPOSITS AND MALABSORPTION SYNDROME

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Abstract

Calcium homeostasis plays an important role in the progression of kidney damage and calcium deposits in the kidneys especially in patients with malabsorption syndrome (MAS).

The research aimed to evaluate calcium homeostasis in kidney damage and calcium deposits in the kidneys in patients with MAS.

Methods. In this study, 109 kidney damage patients with MAS were enrolled. The patients were divided into 4 groups according to the CKD stage and the presence of MAS. Group I included 27 patients with kidney damage without MAS; Group II consisted of 28 patients with kidney damage and MAS; Group III (n = 26) and Group IV (n = 28) included patients with kidney damage without and with MAS and calcium deposits in the kidneys, respectively. According to the morphological study of *in vivo* biopsies of the small intestinal mucosa, mild and moderate morphological changes were observed among all patients. The levels of calcium, phosphorus, parathyroid hormone, osteocalcin, and calcitonin in the blood, as well as urinary calcium levels, were detected.

Results. Pathological changes in calcium metabolism were observed among kidney damage patients with MAS and calcium deposits in the kidneys. These verity of calcium homeostasis disorders was more evident among patients with calcium deposits in the kidneys and MAS. Urinary calcium levels were reduced in the patients of Groups III and IV. No changes were detected in phosphorus levels. Changes in parathyroid hormone and osteocalcin are caused primarily by combined renal pathology with impaired renal calcium absorption.

Conclusion. MAS and calcium deposits in the kidneys patients leads to deep violations of calcium homeostasis resulting in rapid kidney damage progression and bone tissue violation.

Keywords: malabsorption syndrome, kidney damage, calcium deposits.

Introduction. Now, the great importance of metabolic disorders and chronic intestinal diseases in the formation of combined pathology of the kidneys and digestive organs has been proven [1-4]. However, there are no data on the role of factors or non-microbial etiology that form the combined pathology of the kidneys and digestive organs.

Malabsorption syndrome (MAS) combine all types of pathology caused by indigestion or absorption. Among the huge range of diseases with impaired intestinal absorption syndrome, the most common in the therapeutic practice is lactase deficiency, exudative enteropathy, food allergy, Crohn's disease, nonspecific ulcerative colitis, and helminthic invasion, chronic pancreatitis [5,6]. So far, there are little data on the role of factors of non-microbial etiology, that form a combined pathology of the kidneys and gastrointestinal tract. There is no well-developed program for early diagnosis, prevention of development and progression of this pathology [7-9].

Calcium homeostasis plays a crucial role in the progression of kidney damage [10-13], especially in patients with MAS [14-17].

This study aimed to evaluate calcium homeostasis in kidney damage and calcium deposits in the kidneys in patients with MAS.

Patients and methods. A total of 109 kidney damage patients with MAS were included in this study. All patients were treated in the Department of Nephrology of the Chernivtsi Regional Clinical Hospital. There were 94 women and 15 men aged 53.5 ± 7.5 years. Also, 20 healthy individuals of the appropriate age

were examined. In most of the examined patients, the cause of malabsorption syndrome was chronic pancreatitis [2]. The kidney damage causes included tubulointerstitial nephritis and dysmetabolic nephropathy. The patients were divided into 4 groups according to the kidney damage and the presence of MAS. Group I included 27 patients with kidney damage without MAS; Group II consisted of 28 patients with kidney damage, and MAS; Group III (n = 26) and Group IV (n = 28) included patients in kidney damage and calcium deposits in the kidneys without and with MAS, respectively.

There was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki in 1964, revised in 2008. All patients provided an informed written consent to participate in the study. The study protocol was approved by the Local Ethics Commission of Bukovinian State Medical University.

Inclusion criteria were: patients with kidney damage and calcium deposits in the kidneys and MAS, age of patients from 18 to 60 years, glomerular filtration rate (GFR) > 60 ml/min/1.73 m².

Exclusion criteria were: chronic glomerulonephritis or other immune-mediated kidney diseases, systemic connective tissue disease, neoplasm, tuberculosis, and refusal to participate in the study.

In addition to routine clinical and laboratory data (hemoglobin (Hb), glucose, albumin, urine tests, GFR, ultrasound), blood calcium and phosphorus levels were determined using standard kits in a certified laboratory of the regional clinical hospital. Moreover, the levels of parathyroid hormone and calcitonin were studied by

enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using standard kits from "CIS BioInternational" (France). The level of non-collagenous osteocalcin protein, which is a marker of osteoporosis and plays an important role in the formation of the organic matrix of bone tissue was determined to evaluate the activity of osteoporosis and bone loss. Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using the standard kit from Roche Diagnostics (Switzerland) was applied to study the level of osteocalcin in the serum.

The diagnosis of MAS was confirmed by *in vivo* biopsies of the small intestinal mucosa; mild and moderate morphological changes were observed among the enrolled patients. Crypt deepening, decreased small intestinal villus height, (without atrophy), the change in the length of villi and crypt depth correlation, the increase in the number of lymphohistiocytic and plasma

cells in the plate, and change in enterocytes were typical morphological signs of the moderate severity of the process.

Statistical analysis was done with NCSS 2007 package program. The data was presented as mean (M) and standard deviation (SD); the Student t-test was used to compare the differences between the groups. The results were considered significant if the p -value < 0.05 .

Results. The study showed that calcium and parathormone levels in kidney damage patients with MAS had significantly severe disorders compared with those without MAS (Table 1). Urinary calcium levels were significantly reduced among patients of Groups III and IV ($p < 0.05$), which was associated with calcium deposits in the kidneys. Phosphate, osteocalcin and calcitonin levels did not differ between the studied groups.

Table 1

Calcium, phosphate and osteoporosis-related hormones in kidney damage patients according to the presence of MAS

Indexes	The patients' groups				
	Healthy (n = 20)	Group I (n = 27)	Group II (n = 28)	Group III (n = 26)	Group IV (n = 28)
Blood calcium (mmol/l)	2.20±0.6	2.24±0.04	1.84±0.02*#	1.81±0.01*	1.79±0.02*
Urine calcium (mmol/day)	4.25±2.34	3.75±1.24	4.02±1.92	1.03±0.8*	0.95±0.85*
Phosphorus (mmol/l)	0.81±0.99	0.82±0.03	0.83±0.31	0.89±0.24	0.92±0.12
Osteocalcin (ng/l)	25.4±61.98	71.28±3.27	72.73±1.12	79.82±1.12	99.21±0.13*#
Parathyroid hormone (pg/ml)	9.85±6.94	49.33±9.12	58.42±8.63	50.99±8.99	92.45±8.19*#
Calcitonin (pg/ml)	7.22±11.91	8.69±2.11	8.01±2.33	7.98±3.01	8.83±2.74

Notes: * - p -values < 0.05 in comparison with the healthy control;

- p -values < 0.05 in comparison between the studied groups.

It should also be noted that patients with morphologically severe changes in the intestinal mucosa had lower calcium levels (Table 2).

Table 2

Comparative characteristics of calcium and phosphate indicators depending on the severity of morphological lesions

Indicators	The severity of morphological lesion complexity	
	Mild	Moderate
Calcium (mmol/l)	2.24±0.05	2.17±0.03
Phosphorus (mmol/l)	1.46±0.05	1.22±0.02

Discussion. The previous studies have reported an important role of calcium homeostasis in kidney damage progression [1-4] and pointed out its significant disorders in patients with digestive disorders [12-14]. The present study aimed to investigate blood calcium and phosphorus levels, concentrations of calcium-regulating hormones, and urinary calcium in patients with kidney damage and calcium deposits in the kidneys depending on the presence of MAS.

Our results showed that the kidney damage patients with MAS had significant changes in calcium metabolism compared with the patients without MAS. The severity of the sedis orders was higher among the patients with kidney damage patients with calcium deposits in the kidneys compared with those with kidney damage patients with outcalcium deposits in the kidneys. No changes in serum phosphate levels were found in

many of the patient groups. Changes in parathyroid hormone and osteocalcin with some manifestations of osteoporosis, which were confirmed radiologically, in our opinion, are primarily due to combined renal pathology with impaired renal calcium absorption. The obtained results have been demonstrated by other authors in patients with pancreatitis and other gastrointestinal disorders [10, 11, 14, 15]. Calcium levels in daily urine were reduced among Groups III and IV patients, while blood concentrations of calcitonin and phosphorus did not change in all examined kidney damage patients, which contradicts some published studies [15-17]. In our opinion, it could be associated with calcium and active vitamin D prescription in patients with kidney damage with calcium deposits in the kidneys.

Moreover, in the present study, we demonstrated a significant decrease in serum calcium levels in kidney damage patients with severe morphological changes in

the intestinal mucosa. It should be noted, that there was no overt morphological lesion of the intestine since MAS was the result of chronic pancreatitis in almost all examined patients[7-9].

Conclusions. Pathological changes in calcium metabolism were observed in patients with kidney damage and MAS. The severity of these disorders was higher in patients with kidney damage with calcium deposits in the kidneys. Changes in parathyroid hormone and osteocalcin with some manifestations of osteoporosis, in our opinion, are primarily associated with combined renal pathology with impaired absorption of calcium by the kidneys. MAS in kidney damage with calcium deposits in the kidneys patients is serious comorbidity that requires further large-scale studies.

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